

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable D1.6

FRM surface temperature
datasets

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**ARCTIC
PASSION**

Work package 1

Establishing an adaptive and more complete Arctic observing system

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1. Executive summary

The key motivation behind Arctic PASSION is to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. It aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving, and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge. It also aims at streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services, and to contribute to ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system.

This document describes the data sets produced by DMI and its collaborators in Work Package 1 of the Arctic PASSION project. Furthermore, the value and concepts of Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM) in relation to perform end-to-end calibration of satellite products is explained and the total uncertainty of in situ temperature measurements is estimated.

Three Arctic PASSION data sets are produced in accordance with the main goals of WP 1, namely to contribute to an integrated Arctic observing system that integrates the satellite observation system with traditional ground-based observation. The goal is to produce data sets that feed into other WPs of the project and to facilitate process studies, operational activities, reanalysis, prediction, management and climate models.

More specifically, the three DMI data sets contribute to satellite end-to-end calibration activities, to model evaluation (WP3) and supplement the Pilot Service 6 (PS6) 'Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas'.

The data sets that have been produced are: 1) a 10-year temperature (and more) in situ data set of sea ice in North-west Greenland (AP-InSitu), 2) a 43-year long global monthly mean sea ice surface temperature data set (AP-MMIST), and 3) a 10-year Risk Index Outcome (RIO) data set that can act as climatological reference for operational RIO data for ships navigating in ice-infested waters, and as a ship routing planning tool.

All data sets are uploaded to public data portals, or in process of being approved by these, for free and unlimited access. The data set are registered in the SAON data portal (<https://data.arcticobserving.org/>) that is supported by Arctic PASSION. See Chapter 8 for details.

2. Introduction

The main objective of Work Package 1 is to establish the foundation for a comprehensive Arctic observing system of systems (pan-AOSS) that builds on, coordinates and enhances existing observing infrastructures and networks.

The WP1 will provide vital observations for understanding how the Arctic system is functioning, including process studies and analysis of inter-annual and climate variations and changes. Other objectives of the integrated observing systems is to enable and ease establishing joint planning tools, and common observation protocols and data processing standards that are beneficial to the observing community, as well as to the user communities that will get more standardized data formats.

A comprehensive observation network also requires a system that integrates the satellite observation system with traditional ground-based observations, via thorough knowledge of the relationship between in situ point measurements and area mean measurements from satellite data. This integration of satellite and ground observations is of particular importance in Polar areas, where ground-based observations are sparse, because of the challenging environment. To exploit the full value of ground observations as reference to satellite measurements, thorough knowledge of the full uncertainty budget for this is essential.

Likewise, the quality of the ground measurements is of highest importance. Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRMs) provide exactly the desired high-quality observations. The value and concepts of Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM) in relation to perform end-to-end calibration of satellite products is explained in this report and the total uncertainty of in situ temperature measurements is estimated.

DMI is contributing to the WP1 objectives through the development and production of three Arctic PASSION data sets.

One data set is a ground-based FRM data set, of which the main part is recorded in the vicinity of the DMI field facilities in Qaanaaq (NW Greenland), hereafter *Qaanaaq Winter Observatory* (QWO). This data set includes data from Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) and from Ice Mass balance Buoys (IMB). The primary parameter is surface temperature, but it also embraces several other related parameters, like air temperature and snow/ice interface temperature. This data set is recorded over a period of 11 years.

The second data set produced by DMI in the Arctic PASSION (AP), WP1, is a 44-year long monthly mean Ice Surface Temperature (IST) record. This data set is a strong stand alone data set for e.g. climate analysis and a tool for model evaluation and tuning.

The third data set a reprocessed Risk Index Outcome (RIO) data set. This is produced in support of Pilot Service 6, in WP 4 (PS4.6). The objective of PS4.6 is testing a RIO forecast product,

where the RIO “climatology” is a supplementary tool for navigators to facilitate planning of Ship Routes, based on probability.

The three data sets developed, produced and published by DMI and AP are:

- In situ data set from sea ice (AP-InSitu)
- Global Monthly Mean Surface Temperature data set (AP-MMIST)
- Reprocessed Risk Index Outcome (RIO) data set (AP-RIO)

The document is divided into 8 chapters, starting with summary and this introduction.

In chapter 3 the FRM work done by the DMI team is described. The work estimates the total uncertainty of comparing satellite temperature estimates with in situ observation. The AP In situ data set is described in chapter 4. This includes a description of the measured variables and an overview of the temporal coverage of the measurements.

In chapter 5, the AP Monthly Mean Polar surface temperature dataset is described and the AP RIO data set is described in chapter 6.

The internal and external collaboration related to this work is explained in chapter 7, and, finally, in chapter 8, it is explained how to access the 3 DMI-AP data sets.

3. Fiducial reference measurements

Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM) are independent and fully characterized measurements, designed to perform end-to-end calibration of satellite products, where post launch evaluation of sensors is not possible.

A fully characterized FRM is fully described with respect to error, bias, uncertainty and time, place and condition of a recording. All FRM are traceable to S.I. units through the lifetime of a given FRM platform, if possible by applying both pre deployment and post deployment calibrations and routine verification with reference standards. The FRM requirements outlined above are specified in details in the guidelines from the GEO/CEOS Quality Assurance framework for Earth Observation (QA4EO, <https://qa4eo.org/>).

FRM measurements of Sea surface temperature

Only few observational networks or systems live fully up to the FRM requirements, but a true FRM observation network is the ESA funded International Sea Surface Temperature (SST) Fiducial Reference Measurement (FRM) Radiometer Network (ISFRN, <https://ships4sst.org/>), that provides observations from geographically wide-spread seas. This includes the FRM SST

from the North Atlantic provided by the DMI ISAR instrument and data processing system. These data are very relevant in the context of Arctic PASSION and freely available from the project site (<https://ships4sst.org/services/ships4sst-data>). We will ensure that these data are visible for the AP Integrated observing system in order to be frequently harvested by the SAON data portal.

FRM measurements of Sea ice temperature

Ice surface temperature validation work and SI traceability is a sparsely exploited research area. Although challenging, it becomes increasingly important that efforts are made to establish FRM of sea ice surface temperature (IST). Given the issues related to extreme conditions, there have been relatively few field campaigns to date. The establishment of IST FRM is therefore less mature than FRM's for Sea and Land surface temperatures, SST and LST, respectively. Since ice is often significantly colder than most of the other IR radiometer measurements from sea or land, it is important to ensure that radiometers are validated appropriately for this temperature and climate.

Since the early 2010s DMI has continuously recorded Arctic observations from sea ice, with the purpose to validate satellite data. Also dedicated campaigns, led by DMI, have attempted to quantify the uncertainty budget for satellite and in situ comparison over sea ice and to perform sensor intercomparison campaigns (Høyer et al., 2017a and 2017b).

The four vertically stratified temperatures in figure 1, illustrate the main issues related to using in situ temperature records as reference for satellite IST. The data show that snow-ice interface temperatures often can differ 10 K from the associated snow skin temperature. A rule of thumb is that skin and snowpack temperatures can differ approximately by 1 K per centimeter snow separating the surface from the snowpack position. The data in figure 1 also show occasionally large differences between skin, 1 mT and 2 mT measurements.

Figure 1. One week of co-located temperature measurements from sea ice in Inglefield Bredning, Qaanaaq. The 4 temperatures are 2 mT (green), 1 mT (red), snow surface temperature (radiometer, dark blue) and snow-ice interface temperature (9 cm snow, turquoise).

The observations in figure 1 show the challenges when comparing satellite IST estimates with traditional in situ sea ice platforms. Temperature sensors on drifting buoys are most likely covered in some unknown depth of snow, and air temperatures from sea ice platforms are rarely specified by height over the snow surface. In addition to issues associated with the vertical position of a given temperature sensor over sea ice, the spatial temperature variability within a satellite footprint and the temporal sampling difference between recording of reference and satellite overpass also contribute to the total uncertainty of comparing satellite and traditional in situ observations.

Høyer et al. (2017b) computed this uncertainty for radiometric temperatures, traditional buoy temperatures and for 2 mT air temperatures, within 1 km x 1 km satellite footprint, and for sampling mismatch of 10, 30 and 60 minutes. This work resulted in the uncertainty budget listed in table 1.

Table 1 Estimates for components in the uncertainty budget, when comparing the satellite versus in situ observations (Høyer et al., 2017b).

Δx (km)	Δt (min)	Δz (m)	$\mu_{in situ}$ (°C)	$\mu_{\Delta x}$ (°C)	$\mu_{\Delta t}$ (°C)	$\mu_{\Delta z}$ (°C)	$\sqrt{\mu_{in situ}^2 + \mu_{\Delta x}^2 + \mu_{\Delta t}^2 + \mu_{\Delta z}^2}$ (°C)
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1.0	10	IST_{skin}	0.2	0.12-0.25	0.34	0	0.41-0.47
1.0	30	IST_{skin}	0.2	0.12-0.25	0.71	0	0.75-0.78
1.0	60	IST_{skin}	0.2	0.12-0.25	1.11	0	1.13-1.16
1.0	10	T_{2m}	0.05	0.12-0.25	0.34	1.45 - 2.38	1.49-2.42
1.0	30	T_{2m}	0.05	0.12-0.25	0.71	1.45 - 2.38	1.62-2.50
1.0	60	T_{2m}	0.05	0.12-0.25	1.11	1.45 - 2.38	1.83-2.64
1.0	10	T_{buoy}	0.05	0.12-0.25	0.34	3.27 - 4.95	3.29-4.97
1.0	30	T_{buoy}	0.05	0.12-0.25	0.71	3.27 - 4.95	3.35-5.01
1.0	60	T_{buoy}	0.05	0.12-0.25	1.11	3.27 - 4.95	3.46-5.08

Some specific assumptions have been made in filling in table 1.

These include:

- The radiometric uncertainty is estimated to 0.2 °C (see Høyer et al., 2017a)
- The iSVP buoy sensor uncertainty is estimated to 0.05 °C, according to specifications
- The AWS pt100 sensor uncertainty is estimated to 0.05 °C for T_{2m}
- The range for $\mu_{\Delta z}$ for T_{2m} arise from two intervals: windsp. ≥ 3 m/s and windsp. < 3 m/s, where the $\mu_{in situ}$ contributions have been subtracted
- The range for $\mu_{\Delta z}$ for T_{buoy} are derived from the four iSVP buoys compared against the IST_{skin} from the AWS where the $\mu_{in situ}$ have been subtracted

Following this uncertainty scheme, the smallest uncertainties are associated with radiometric references, with the smallest temporal mismatch between reference and satellite recording. The largest uncertainty is associated with traditional buoy measurements. The total uncertainties for these 2 extremes are 0.4 K and 5.1 K, respectively.

Uncertainties of snow skin temperature estimates from Ice Mass Balance buoys are assumed to be similar to uncertainties from thermal radiometers.

In situ temperature data from Automatic Weather Stations on fast ice in the Inglefield Bredning have been compiled into an Arctic PASSION in situ data set (Chapter 4). The total uncertainties and uncertainties of dominating uncertainty components of the temperature are listed in table 1.

Figure 3 The four main instruments in the QWO sea ice and snow program from deployed situations in Ingfield Bredning, Qaanaaq. *OldAWS* (top-left), *NewAWS* (top-right), *MiniAWS* (bottom left) and *IMB* (bottom right).

The deployment periods of the four in situ observation systems that are included in the AP-InSitu data set is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4 The deployment periods of the 4 observation systems of the AP-InSitu data set: Old AWS (top, CR1000), the New AWS (second from top, CR1000X New), the Mini AWS (CR1000X mini, second from the bottom) and IMB deployments (bottom group). IMB deployments are divided into DMI and NAACOS, representing deployments near QWO and 7 deployments in 2012 in the Arctic ocean.

Methods and processing

The AP-InSitu data set is produced from annual deployments of one or more of the DMI AWS systems and an IMB. The deployment procedure is an early winter deployment in December or January (when the fast ice is reliable for transport). The recording period goes until the beginning of June, when the fast ice usually breaks up, or before, if break-up is earlier than normal. Then all AWS's and instruments are retrieved, and data are downloaded.

The task in AP is to compile, standardize, store and publish the data sets. Examples of temperature data from QWO AWS's, are given below in figures 5 and 6 from the Mini- and NewAWS, respectively. An example of a processed DMI IMB data set, by AWI (Preusser et al., 2025), is shown in figure 7.

A complete listing of all measured or deduced parameters in the AP-InSitu data set is given in the following section.

Figure 5 DMI *MiniAWS* Inglefield Bredning, Qaanaq, NW Greenland. Air and snow/ice interface temperatures are recorded by PT100 and the Tskin is recorded by IR120

Figure 6 Skin temperature measured along with 1, 2 and 4 meter air temperatures and 3 snow/ice interface temperatures from *NewAWS*.

Figure 7 A Processed DMI IMB data set from Qaanaq 2023. Processing is carried out by AWI, using the SIMBA IMB reprocessing software developed by AWI (Preusser et al., 2025).

Data output

The AP-InSitu data is created both as daily files containing all AWS's as well as yearly files for each of the measuring stations. The parameters for each of the dataloggers can be seen in tables 2-4. All parameters measured or deduced/estimated from the IMB is described at the end of this section.

All data are stored in NetCDF format and in compliance with CF conventions v1.6, where possible.

Table 2 Parameters measured by OldAWS.

Parameter	Parameter long name	Units
TIMESTAMP	Date and timestamp	TS
RECORD	Record no.	RN
RH	RelativeHumidity	%
SR01Up_avg	IncomingShortWaveRadiation_aver age	W/m ²
SR01Dn_Avg	OutgoingShortWaveRadiation_aver age	W/m ²
IR01Up_Avg	IncomingLongWaveRadiation_averag e	W/m ²
IR01Dn_Avg	OutgoingLongWaveRadiation_averag e	W/m ²
Albedo_Avg	Albedo, outgoingSW/incomingSW	W/m ²
UpTot_Avg	Total_Incoming_SW+LW	W/m ²
DnTot_Avg	Total_outgoing_SW+LW	W/m ²
NetTot_avg	Total Net Radiation, Incoming_total - outgoing_total	W/m ²
IR01UpCo_Avg	INcomingLWradiation_plus_StefanBo ltzmannLaw_totalEmitted_Energy_SB const*T4	W/m ²
Ir01DnCo_Avg	OutgoingLWradiation_plus_StefanBol tzmannLaw_totalEmitted_Energy_SB const*T4	W/m ²
PT100_C_1_Avg	SnowIce_interfaceTemp1	Deg C
PT100_C_2_Avg	SnowIce_interfaceTemp2	Deg C

PT100_C_3_Avg	SnowIce_interfaceTemp3	Deg C
PT100_C_4_Avg	SnowIce_interfaceTemp4	Deg C
T107_C_Avg	airTemp_1m	Deg C
WS_ms_S_WVT	Wind_Speed_4m_check_notes	meters/second
WindDir_D1_WVT	WindDirection	Deg
AVG_Surface_Temperature_C_1	Radiometric_surface_Temp_C_emiss=1	Deg C
Latitude_Degrees	Latitude_Degrees	degrees
Latitude_Minutes	Latitude_Minutes	minutes
Longitude_Degrees	Longitude_Degrees	degrees
Longitude_Minutes	Longitude_Minutes	minutes
Snow_Depth_Avg	Snow_Depth_incl_offset(instrument_height)	Meters

Table 3 Parameters measured by NewAWS.

Parameter	Parameter long name	Units
DATESTAMP	DATE_AND_TIMESTAMP	DS
RECORD	Record_no	RN
WS_ms_S_WVT	windspeed_1m	meters/second
WindDir_D1_WVT	WindDir_1m_D1	Deg
WS_ms_S_WVT1	windspeed_2m	meters/second
WindDir_D1_WVT1	WindDir_2m_D1	Deg
WS_ms_S_WVT2	windspeed_4m	meters/second

WindDir_D1_WVT2	WindDir_4m_D1	Deg
T107_C_1_Avg	airTemp_1m	Deg C
T107_C_2_Avg	airTemp_4m	Deg C
AirTC_Avg	airTemp_2m	Deg C
RelativeHumidity	RelativeHumidity	%
Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg	SnowIcE_interfaceTemp1	Deg C
Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg	SnowIcE_interfaceTemp2	Deg C
Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg	SnowIcE_interfaceTemp3	Deg C
DT_Avg	SnowPingDist_offset	m (e.g. offset=1.42)
AVG_Surface_Temperature_C	Radiometric_surface_Temp_C_emiss =1	Deg C

Table 4 Parameters measured by MiniAWS.

Parameter	Parameter long name	Units
TIMESTAMP	TIMESTAMP	TS
RECORD	Record_no	RN
PTemp_C_Avg	Panel_Temperature_C	Deg C
Temp_C_1_Avg	SnowIcE_interfaceTemp_avg_(check_conf)	Deg C
Temp_C_2_Avg	airTemp_2m_avg_(check_conf)	Deg C
AVG_Surface_Temperature_C	Radiometric_surface_Temp_C_emiss =1	Deg C

IMB

The unprocessed IMB data record consists of 240 temperatures per time interval, vertically separated by 2 cm, from approximately 50 cm above the ice down through air, snow, ice and the upper water column (see figure 7).

The processed IMB data consists of snow depth, ice thickness associated to each temperature sampling, each 3 hours.

5. Monthly Mean IST (AP-MMIST)

The Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and the Arctic PASSION WP1.2 have jointly developed and produced a Monthly Mean temperature data set for Polar Regions. Here named AP-MMIST.

Product description

The Arctic PASSION Polar Monthly Mean IST product (AP-MMIST) is a combined surface temperature product covering open ocean, marginal ice zone and closed sea ice areas, represented by Sea Surface Temperatures (SST), Marginal Ice Zone Temperatures (MIZT) and sea Ice Surface Temperatures (IST). Besides ocean and sea ice the data set also includes surface temperatures from the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets.

AP-MMIST is produced jointly by Arctic PASSION WP-1 and the Sea Ice Thematic Assembly Centre (Sea Ice TAC) under the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S - service contract: 2022/C3S2_312b_MOi_SC1).

The main product variable is a monthly average based on daily mean Surface Temperatures from the C3S IST CDR v1.0 and ICDR v1.1 data sets.

AP-MMIST product specifications:

- Variables:
 - ST: Monthly Mean Surface temperature (Integrated ocean, sea ice and marginal ice zone surface temperature and Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets)
 - STmax: The maximum pixel value within the given month
 - STmin: The minimum pixel value within the given month
 - Counts: Number of daily temperatures that a given MMIST pixel value is based on.
- Temporal coverage: 1982-2024
- Geographical coverage: Pole-wards of 50 N and 50 S
- Spatial resolution: 0.25 degrees
- Projection: Regular geographical grid
- Product type: Level 3 (Fixed projection with data gaps)

Methods and processing

The AP-MMIST is a monthly averaged temperature product based the C3S daily IST CDR and ICDR level 3 data. The daily mean C3S IST data set is a resampled and averaged daily mean IST product using Global Area Coverage AVHRR IST level 2 data as input. The level 2 and 3 CDR and

ICDR data records are described in Algorithm Theoretical baseline Document (Eastwood et al., 2024a).

The surface temperature retrieval algorithm used to produce the basic level 2 product is a traditional split window algorithm using two Thermal InfraRed (TIR) channels to compensate for atmosphere and angular emissivity dependency. This is described in the Algorithm Theoretical baseline Document (Eastwood et al., 2024b). The level 1 TIR input data set is the full data record from the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer's (AVHRR) on-board NOAA satellite platforms since 1982, as well as AVHRR records on-board Metop satellites since 2006.

In figure 8 Winter sample of the AP-MMIST from the Arctic and Antarctic regions are shown, from March and September, respectively.

Figure 8 The Arctic PASSION and C3S MM-IST product examples from March and September 2024, for the Northern (left) and Southern (right) Hemispheres, respectively. Both plots have identical temperature scales.

Besides the monthly mean surface temperatures that have a value in themselves and for large scale model evaluations, the AP-MMIST is an excellent data set for climate assessments of the polar temperatures. From the AP-MMIST, surface temperature climatology can easily be calculated, and time series analysis of the data set will provide an overview of inter-annual variability and indications of trends, both on Polar and local scales.

In figure 9, for example, the AP-MMIST data set is used to plot time series of the surface temperatures in the Arctic Ocean and of the West Antarctic Ice sheet.

Figure 9 Time series of the Arctic Ocean (top) and West Antarctic (bottom) from June 1982 to November 2024. The Arctic Ocean includes The Greenland Sea and the Barents Sea, exclusive the coastal areas of the Arctic Ocean. West Antarctica includes most of the Ice Sheet and the adjacent seas. Red dots show the monthly mean temperature, and the shaded area illustrates the full range of the data.

Data output and data access

The product output formats is NetCDF with standard attributes, following CF convention to the degree possible. The monthly data are divided into 2 monthly files, one for each hemisphere, SH and NH.

A dump of the product file content, including variables and attributes, is included in Appendix B.

6. Risk Index Outcome (AP-RIO)

The Risk Index Outcome (RIO) is a critical component of the Polar Operational Limit Assessment Risk Indexing System (POLARIS) developed by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). RIO evaluates the operational risks for ships navigating in ice-infested waters by evaluating ice conditions and offers a quantifiable measure of risk that aids in decision-making for safe navigation in Polar Regions based on ship ice class, sea ice type/stage of development (SOD) and sea ice concentration (SIC).

Product description

The DMI-led Automated Sea Ice Products (ASIP, Wulf et al., 2024) provides daily maps of SOD and SIC based on Sentinel-1 SAR imagery, AMSR-2 Passive Microwave and Ice Charts from the DMI Ice Service, combined with novel AI retrieval and processing techniques.

By leveraging these detailed datasets, the Arctic PASSION- RIO (AP-RIO) data will enhance the safety and efficiency of maritime operations in the polar seas, providing a robust reference for evaluating normal and extreme ice conditions.

The AP-RIO dataset will provide weekly risk assessment maps for the given ship classes and will support the establishment of a 10-year climatology thereby enabling the assessment of RIO variability in the years covered by the input ASIP products.

From the reprocessed RIO data, a RIO climatology can be established, and the RIO variability can be assessed. These data can be used as reference for daily RIO information to evaluate a given situation as e.g. "normal" or "extreme".

Method and processing

Algorithm and Processing Scheme

- Daily sea ice variables from ASIP are processed into weekly fields. The Sea Ice Concentration (SIC) is calculated as the statistical mean of the daily values, while the Stage of Development (SOD) is computed as the statistical mode, which corresponds to the most frequently occurring value among the daily SOD values within the week. This is done for the time period of 3 Oct. 2014 - 31. Dec. 2024
- The weekly SODs are used to find the Risk Value (RV) by looking at the lookup table in Table 5.
- Risk Index Outcome (RIO) values are computed based on the RIO formula (eq. 1) using the SIC from ASIP and the found RV, for each pixel in the field.

- Meaning of the computed RIO values can be interpreted using Table 6.
- The RIO field is saved to weekly NetCDF files.

Table 5 Risk Value (RV) lookup table based on SOD from ASIP

		Risk Values (RVs)				
Polar Ship Category	Ice Class	Ice Free	New/Young Ice	Thin FY Ice	Thick FY Ice	MY Ice
		-	0 - 30 cm	30 - 70 cm	70 - 200 cm	>200 cm
		SOD = <0	SOD = 0	SOD = 1	SOD = 2	SOD = 3
A	PC1	3	3	2	2	1
	PC2	3	3	2	2	0
	PC3	3	3	2	2	-1
	PC4	3	3	2	1	-2
	PC5	3	3	2	0	-2
B	PC6	3	2	1	-1	-3
	PC7	3	2	1	-2	-3
C	1A Super	3	1	1	-2	-4
	1A	3	1	0	-3	-5
	1B	3	1	-1	-4	-6
	1C	3	0	-2	-5	-8
	No Class	3	-1	-3	-6	-8

The equation 1 shows the formula to compute RIO value for a pixel

$$EQ1 \quad RIO = SIC \cdot RV$$

Table 6 The RIO classes for the 3 selected Ship classes.

Available safe mode of operations	PC1 - PC7	1a Super, 1A	1B, 1C, No Class
Independent operation	$RIO \geq 0$	$RIO \geq 0$	$RIO \geq 0$
Independent operation with limited speed or icebreaker escorted operation	$-10 \leq RIO < 0$		
Icebreaker escorted operation only		$-10 \leq RIO < 0$	$-10 \leq RIO < 0$
Icebreaker escorted operation with limited speed	$-20 \leq RIO < -10$	$-20 \leq RIO < -10$	
Operation is not safe	$RIO < -20$	$RIO < -20$	$RIO < -20$

RIO plots for 3 different classes

In the first version of the AP RIO dataset we provide indices related to three different ship classes (PC2, PC7 and 1C) due to netCDF file size as RIO indexes were generated with the high resolution ASIP dataset. Those three ship classes cover the full spectrum of ship classes designed to operate in elevated operational risk.

Figure 10 Stage of development (From ASIP, Left), Sea Ice Concentration (From ASIP, Middle) and RIO risk map (Right) of the arctic waters, for Shipclass PC2. For the week of 26/01/2018 to 01/02/2018.

Figure 11 Stage of development (From ASIP, Left), Sea Ice Concentration (From ASIP, Middle) and RIO risk map (Right) of the arctic waters, for Shipclass 1C. For the week of 26/01/2018 to 01/02/2018.

Data output

The product output formats are NetCDF with standard attributes, following CF convention to the degree possible.

A dump of the product file content, including variables and attributes is included in Appendix C.

7. Collaborations

The DMI AP data sets are all products created through interaction with both internal and external partners and/or projects

Collaborations with other tasks/WP

The AP-InSitu data set is partly an AP-DMI product and partly a AP-DMI-AWI collaboration. The joint interest in comparing temperature observations from the DMI FRM observations network with the AWI IMB re-processor has been very useful.

The global monthly mean IST has no internal AP partners or collaborators. However, it is a product useful for model evaluation (WP3) for e.g. evaluating large scale model performance. for the data set is also well suited for calculating local trends or trends on large scale, as well as an easy tool for calculating temperature climatology in Polar Regions.

The reprocessed RIO data set is made in collaboration with partners of, and in support to Pilot Service PS6. PS6 is testing a RIO forecast product based on a coupled ocean and sea ice model. The RIO climatology is aiming to be a tool for planning of ship routes and in some cases to evaluate a given ice situation – whether it is a normal or an extreme situation.

External collaborations

The production of the global Monthly Mean IST climate data record is carried out in collaboration with the Sea Ice TAC under C3S (service contract: 2022/C3S2_312b_MOi_SC1), and in collaboration with the Ocean and Sea Ice team at MET Norway.

The main input to the RIO data set is the reprocessed high resolution sea ice concentration and type data set, ASIP. ASIP is built on a series of projects, both ESA and internal DMI funding (National Centre of Climate Research, NCKF), but initiated by the Danish Ministry of Innovation, as a novel Machine learning based algorithm to estimate high resolution sea ice products automatically.

8. Impact and exploitation

All three data sets are uploaded, archived and published or in review for publishing in Meereisportal, Pangaea or Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS).

The AP-InSitu data set, including AWS and IMB data, will be published continuously on MeereisPortal.de (**Grosfeld et al., 2016**). Soon after being available on Meereisportal, all data will be pushed to Pangaea.de (Felden et al., 2023) to be published and to obtain a DOI. Future in situ data sets from QWO will be processed and made available following the procedure above.

The AP-MMIST data set is registered and uploaded to the Pangaea in January 2025 (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.975011>). The data set is also published and made available from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS). Here the full data set is listed (with a URL for each monthly file) in a so-called Pseudo-Manifest file that can be retrieved from a browser or by using *wget* in a terminal (`wget http://cataloguedata-ecv.data.compute.cci1.ecmwf.int/data5/si-temperature/c3s_manifest/pseudomanifest_Moi_IST_CDR_v1.0.txt [--no-proxy]`). The data files in the manifest file can be retrieved like-wise.

The Arctic PASSION RIO data set (AP-RIO) is registered and uploaded to Pangaea (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.975054>).

The data on Pangaea will automatically be harvested by SAON.

9. Acknowledgment

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Finally, we wish to thank the National Climate Research Center (NCKF) and DMI for annual donations to the QWO. The annual donations efficiently contribute to the continuous collection

of observations from above, on, in and under sea ice, that among other things provide priceless reference data for the satellite based surface temperature products.

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APPENDIX

Examples of the output formats of the 3 products (netcdf header dumps).

In situ data (AP-InSitu data set), Monthly Mean IST (AP-MMIST) and reprocessed RIO data set (AP-RIO), in APPENDIX A, B and C, respectively

APPENDIX A

NetCDF file example of In Situ data set

The file content is a raw dump that will be standardized and cleaned for irrelevant or dubious content:

```
netcdf \2022_2023_cr1000x_new_in_situ_data_qaanaaq {
```

dimensions:

```
    time_of_obs = 47657 ;
```

variables:

```
    double RECORD(time_of_obs) ;
```

```
        RECORD:_FillValue = NaN ;
```

```
        RECORD:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
```

```
        RECORD:standard_name = "RECORD" ;
```

```
        RECORD:long_name = "Record number of this observation series." ;
```

```
        RECORD:units = "#" ;
```

```
        RECORD:valid_min = 0LL ;
```

```
        RECORD:valid_max = 999999999LL ;
```

```
    double WS_ms_S_WVT(time_of_obs) ;
```

```
        WS_ms_S_WVT:_FillValue = NaN ;
```

```
        WS_ms_S_WVT:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
```

```
        WS_ms_S_WVT:standard_name = "WS_ms_S_WVT" ;
```

```
        WS_ms_S_WVT:long_name = "windspeed at 1m" ;
```

```
        WS_ms_S_WVT:units = "m/s" ;
```



```

WS_ms_S_WVT:valid_min = 0LL ;
WS_ms_S_WVT:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WindDir_D1_WVT(time_of_obs) ;

WindDir_D1_WVT:_FillValue = NaN ;
WindDir_D1_WVT:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WindDir_D1_WVT:standard_name = "WindDir_D1_WVT" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT:long_name = "Wind direction at 1m D1" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT:units = "Degrees" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT:valid_min = 0LL ;
WindDir_D1_WVT:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WindDir_SD1_WVT(time_of_obs) ;

WindDir_SD1_WVT:_FillValue = NaN ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT:standard_name = "WindDir_SD1_WVT" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT:long_name = "Wind direction at 1m SD1" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT:units = "Degrees" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT:valid_min = 0LL ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WS_ms_S_WVT1(time_of_obs) ;

WS_ms_S_WVT1:_FillValue = NaN ;
WS_ms_S_WVT1:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WS_ms_S_WVT1:standard_name = "WS_ms_S_WVT1" ;
WS_ms_S_WVT1:long_name = "Windspeed at 2m" ;
WS_ms_S_WVT1:units = "m/s" ;
WS_ms_S_WVT1:valid_min = 0LL ;
WS_ms_S_WVT1:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WindDir_D1_WVT1(time_of_obs) ;

```



```
WindDir_D1_WVT1:_FillValue = NaN ;
WindDir_D1_WVT1:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WindDir_D1_WVT1:standard_name = "WindDir_D1_WVT1" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT1:long_name = "Wind direction at 2m D1" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT1:units = "Degrees" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT1:valid_min = 0LL ;
WindDir_D1_WVT1:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WindDir_SD1_WVT1(time_of_obs) ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT1:_FillValue = NaN ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT1:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT1:standard_name = "WindDir_SD1_WVT1" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT1:long_name = "Wind direction at 2m SD1" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT1:units = "Degrees" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT1:valid_min = 0LL ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT1:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WS_ms_S_WVT2(time_of_obs) ;
WS_ms_S_WVT2:_FillValue = NaN ;
WS_ms_S_WVT2:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WS_ms_S_WVT2:standard_name = "WS_ms_S_WVT2" ;
WS_ms_S_WVT2:long_name = "Windspeed at 4m" ;
WS_ms_S_WVT2:units = "m/s" ;
WS_ms_S_WVT2:valid_min = 0LL ;
WS_ms_S_WVT2:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WindDir_D1_WVT2(time_of_obs) ;
WindDir_D1_WVT2:_FillValue = NaN ;
WindDir_D1_WVT2:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WindDir_D1_WVT2:standard_name = "WindDir_D1_WVT2" ;
```



```

WindDir_D1_WVT2:long_name = "Wind direction at 4m D1" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT2:units = "Degrees" ;
WindDir_D1_WVT2:valid_min = 0LL ;
WindDir_D1_WVT2:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double WindDir_SD1_WVT2(time_of_obs) ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT2:_FillValue = NaN ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT2:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT2:long_name = "Wind direction at 4m SD1" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT2:units = "Degrees" ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT2:valid_min = 0LL ;
WindDir_SD1_WVT2:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double T107_C_1_Avg(time_of_obs) ;
T107_C_1_Avg:_FillValue = NaN ;
T107_C_1_Avg:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
T107_C_1_Avg:standard_name = "airTemp_1m" ;
T107_C_1_Avg:long_name = "Average temperature of the air temperature
sensor in Degrees Celsius at 1m" ;
T107_C_1_Avg:units = "Degree C" ;
T107_C_1_Avg:valid_min = -90LL ;
T107_C_1_Avg:valid_max = 90LL ;

double T107_C_2_Avg(time_of_obs) ;
T107_C_2_Avg:_FillValue = NaN ;
T107_C_2_Avg:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
T107_C_2_Avg:standard_name = "T107_C_2_Avg" ;
T107_C_2_Avg:long_name = "Average temperature of the air temperature
sensor in Degrees Celsius at 4m" ;
T107_C_2_Avg:units = "Degree C" ;

```



```
T107_C_2_Avg:valid_min = -90LL ;
T107_C_2_Avg:valid_max = 90LL ;

double AirTC_Avg(time_of_obs) ;

AirTC_Avg:_FillValue = NaN ;
AirTC_Avg:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
AirTC_Avg:standard_name = "airTemp_2m" ;

AirTC_Avg:long_name = "Average temperature of the air temperature sensor in
Degrees Celsius at 2m" ;

AirTC_Avg:units = "Degree C" ;
AirTC_Avg:valid_min = 0LL ;
AirTC_Avg:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double RH(time_of_obs) ;

RH:_FillValue = NaN ;
RH:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
RH:standard_name = "RH" ;
RH:long_name = "Relative Humidity" ;
RH:units = "%" ;
RH:valid_min = 0LL ;
RH:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg(time_of_obs) ;

Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg:_FillValue = NaN ;
Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg:standard_name = "Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg" ;
Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg:long_name = "Snow Ice interface Temperature 1" ;
Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg:units = "Degrees C" ;
Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg:valid_min = 0LL ;
Temp_C_1_PT100_Avg:valid_max = 99999LL ;
```



```
double Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg(time_of_obs) ;
    Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg:_FillValue = NaN ;
    Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
    Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg:standard_name = "Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg" ;
    Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg:long_name = "Snow Ice interface Temperature 2" ;
    Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg:units = "Degrees C" ;
    Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg:valid_min = 0LL ;
    Temp_C_2_PT100_Avg:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg(time_of_obs) ;
    Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg:_FillValue = NaN ;
    Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
    Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg:standard_name = "Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg" ;
    Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg:long_name = "Snow Ice interface Temperature 2" ;
    Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg:units = "Degrees C" ;
    Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg:valid_min = 0LL ;
    Temp_C_3_PT100_Avg:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double DT_Avg(time_of_obs) ;
    DT_Avg:_FillValue = NaN ;
    DT_Avg:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
    DT_Avg:standard_name = "SnowPingDist_offset" ;
    DT_Avg:long_name = "-";
    DT_Avg:units = "m" ;
    DT_Avg:valid_min = 0LL ;
    DT_Avg:valid_max = 99999LL ;

double AVG_Surface_Temperature_C(time_of_obs) ;
    AVG_Surface_Temperature_C:_FillValue = NaN ;
    AVG_Surface_Temperature_C:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
```



```

AVG_Surface_Temperature_C:standard_name = "avg_surface_temperature_C" ;
AVG_Surface_Temperature_C:long_name = "Average surface temperature in
degrees Celcius. Radiometric surface temperature" ;
AVG_Surface_Temperature_C:units = "Degrees C" ;
AVG_Surface_Temperature_C:valid_min = -100LL ;
AVG_Surface_Temperature_C:valid_max = 100LL ;
double time_of_obs(time_of_obs) ;
time_of_obs:_FillValue = NaN ;
time_of_obs:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
time_of_obs:standard_name = "time_of_obs" ;
time_of_obs:long_name = "Time of observation." ;
time_of_obs:units = "Seconds since 1970-01-01." ;
time_of_obs:valid_min = 0LL ;
time_of_obs:valid_max = 99999999999LL ;

// global attributes:
:title = "ArcticPASSION-InSitu" ;

:acknowledgement = "Homogenized dataset of AWS observations from DMI\'s
Qaanaaq Winter Observatory, located at IngleField Bredning and Qaanaaq in North Western
Greenland. This data set is recorded with funding by DMI through it local project, Qaanaaq
Winter Observatory" and work with standardizing an dorganizing and publicating the data is
funded by the European Union\'s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the
project Arctic PASSION under grant agreement No. 101003472." ;

:institution = "Danish Meteorological Institute, DMI" ;

:Contact = "gd@dmi.dk or msu@dmi.dk" ;
}

```


APPENDIX B

NetCDF file example of the MM-IST data set:

```
netcdf \202410-DMI_MET-L3S_GHRSSST-STskin-AVHRR_nh_SST_IST-MM_ICDR-v1.1-fv1.0 {
```

dimensions:

```
time = 1 ;
```

```
lat = 160 ;
```

```
lon = 1440 ;
```

variables:

```
int64 time(time) ;
```

```
time:standard_name = "time" ;
```

```
time:long_name = "First time of period." ;
```

```
time:units = "days since 1970-01-01" ;
```

```
time:calendar = "proleptic_gregorian" ;
```

```
float lat(lat) ;
```

```
lat:units = "degrees_north" ;
```

```
lat:long_name = "Latitude" ;
```

```
float lon(lon) ;
```

```
lon:units = "degrees_east" ;
```

```
lon:long_name = "Longitude" ;
```

```
float surface_temperature(time, lat, lon) ;
```

```
surface_temperature:_FillValue = NaNf ;
```

```
surface_temperature:standard_name = "surface_temperature" ;
```

```
surface_temperature:long_name = "Monthly mean sea and ice surface  
temperature" ;
```

```
surface_temperature:units = "K" ;
```

```
int64 N(time, lat, lon) ;
```

```
N:long_name = "Number of daily mean values applied in monthly mean value" ;
```



```

N:units = "1" ;
N:standard_name = "number_of_observations" ;
N:ancillary_variables = "surface_temperature" ;

float t2m(time, lat, lon) ;
t2m:_FillValue = NaNf ;
t2m:standard_name = "air_temperature" ;
t2m:long_name = "Daily mean 2m air temperatures from ERA Interim reanalysis"
;

t2m:units = "K" ;

float surface_temperature_min(time, lat, lon) ;
surface_temperature_min:_FillValue = NaNf ;
surface_temperature_min:standard_name = "surface_temperature" ;
surface_temperature_min:long_name = "Monthly minimum surface
temperature" ;
surface_temperature_min:units = "K" ;

float surface_temperature_max(time, lat, lon) ;
surface_temperature_max:_FillValue = NaNf ;
surface_temperature_max:standard_name = "surface_temperature" ;
surface_temperature_max:long_name = "Monthly maximum surface
temperature" ;
surface_temperature_max:units = "K" ;

float sea_ice_fraction(time, lat, lon) ;
sea_ice_fraction:_FillValue = NaNf ;
sea_ice_fraction:standard_name = "sea_ice_area_fraction" ;
sea_ice_fraction:long_name = "Monthly mean sea ice fraction from OSI-430-a" ;
sea_ice_fraction:units = "1" ;

ubyte surface_type(time, lat, lon) ;
surface_type:units = "1" ;

```



```
surface_type:long_name = "icecap=1, water=2, bedrock=3,  
ETOP01_waterOSISAF_land=4, sea_ice=5" ;
```

```
// global attributes:
```

```
:title = "C3S, Monthly Mean Ice and sea Surface Temperatures (MMIST)" ;
```

```
:institution = "Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)" ;
```

```
:source = "Satellite Observations" ;
```

```
:activity_type = "Space borne instrument(s)" ;
```

```
:start_date = "2024-10-31T23:59Z" ;
```

```
:product_status = "Operational" ;
```

```
:abstract = "The C3S Monthly Mean Ice and sea Surface Temperatures (MMIST)  
product is based on the original work from DMI and MET on the combined Polar ocean and ice  
surface temperature product, originally named \"the Arctic and Antarctic Surface Temperature  
from thermal Infrared satellite sensors\", AASTI. The MMIST provides monthly mean, minimum  
and maximum snow and ice skin temperatures pole-wards of 50 degrees North and South in  
the period from January 1982 and on-wards. Surface temperatures are calculated from thermal  
infrared brightness temperature measurements (Tb) from the Global Area Coverage - Advanced  
Very High Resolution Radiometer (GAC - AVHRR) data. The underlying AASTI algorithm is a  
commonly known split window algorithm that conceptually is applied for numerous land, sea  
and ice retrieval systems. In addition to the IST retrieval, the MMIST also contain Sea Surface  
Temperatures (SST) that are seamlessly estimated through Marginal Ice Zone temperatures that  
are interpolated from IST and SST temperatures." ;
```

```
:spatial_resolution_latitude = "0.25" ;
```

```
:spatial_resolution_longitude = "0.25" ;
```

```
:area = "Arctic" ;
```

```
:southernmost_latitude = "50" ;
```

```
:northernmost_latitude = "90" ;
```

```
:references = "DMI" ;
```

```
:institution_reference = "http://www.dmi.dk/" ;
```

```
:contact = "gd@dmi.dk" ;
```

```
:software_version = "C3S, Monthly Mean Ice and sea Surface Temperature  
version 1.00; C3S-MMISTv1.00" ;
```



```
:comments = "The monthly mean ice and ocean temperature product is
calculated from all available daily mean values of the C3S daily Ice Surface Temperature CDR
version 1.0 and ICDR version 1.1, covering January 1982 to June 2019 and July 2019 - onwards,
respectively. The Number of daily values applied for each monthly mean pixel estimate is given
in the N-variable." ;
```

```
:acknowledgement = "This work is funded and carried out by the Sea Ice Tac
(C3S2_312b) of Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and by the European Union\'s Horizon
2020 research and innovation programme through the project Arctic PASSION under grant
agreement No. 101003472." ;
```

```
:DOI = "" ;
```

```
:grid = "regular geographic grid" ;
```

```
:input_data = "AASTI daily means ICDR v1.1" ;
```

```
:Conventions = "CF-1.6" ;
```

```
}
```

APPENDIX C

NetCDF file example of the RIO data set:

```
netcdf RIO_Lthick_new_PC2_PC7_1C_mean_20150109_20150115 {
```

dimensions:

```
time = UNLIMITED ; // (1 currently)
```

```
yc = 15100 ;
```

```
xc = 10400 ;
```

```
shipclass = 3 ;
```

variables:

```
float lon(yc, xc) ;
```

```
lon:_FillValue = NaNf ;
```

```
lon:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
```

```
lon:standard_name = "longitude" ;
```



```
lon:long_name = "longitude coordinate" ;
lon:units = "degrees_east" ;
lon:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
lon:coordinates = "lon lat" ;

float lat(yc, xc) ;
lat:_FillValue = NaN ;
lat:least_significant_digit = 3LL ;
lat:long_name = "latitude coordinate" ;
lat:standard_name = "latitude" ;
lat:units = "degrees_north" ;
lat:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
lat:coordinates = "lon lat" ;

double time(time) ;
time:_FillValue = NaN ;
time:standard_name = "time" ;
time:units = "days since 1970-01-01" ;
time:calendar = "proleptic_gregorian" ;

double xc(xc) ;
xc:_FillValue = NaN ;
xc:axis = "X" ;
xc:standard_name = "projection_x_coordinate" ;
xc:long_name = "x-coordinate in cartesian system" ;
xc:units = "m" ;

double yc(yc) ;
yc:_FillValue = NaN ;
yc:axis = "Y" ;
yc:standard_name = "projection_y_coordinate" ;
```



```
yc:long_name = "y-coordinate in cartesian system" ;
yc:units = "m" ;
byte shipclass(shipclass) ;
double RIO(time, shipclass, yc, xc) ;
RIO:_FillValue = NaN ;
RIO:long_name = "Risk Index Outcome (POLARIS)" ;
RIO:units = "[]" ;
RIO:comment = "Ship classes included in this file: PC2, PC7, 1C" ;
RIO:comment2 = "Meaning of shipclass-dimension: 1:PC1, 2:PC2, 3:PC3, 4:PC4,
5:PC5, 6:PC6, 7:PC7, 10:1ASuper, 11:1A, 12:1B, 13:1C, 20:noclass" ;
RIO:coordinates = "lat lon" ;
// global attributes:
:title = "Risk Index Outcome (RIO) calculated from DMI\'s ASIP data" ;
:history = "Created by RIOengine_ASIP.py on 2024-12-05" ;
:acknowledgement = "Used RIO calculation method: Lthick_newThis datased has
been funded by the European Union\'s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
through the project Arctic PASSION under grant agreement No. 101003472." ;
:institution = "Danish Meteorological Institute, DMI" ;
:Contact = "gd@dmi.dk or msu@dmi.dk" ;
```

